

The Original Location of Khufu's Coffin

Ian Douglas, B.Sc

ian@zti.co.za

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Abstract

A geometric and astronomical determination of the probable original location of the coffin in the Great Pyramid.

Keywords: Egyptology, Giza, geometry, Great Pyramid, archaeogeometry, archaeoastronomy, ϕ , golden ratio.

Best viewed and printed in colour.

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Revision history:

1.0.0 15 May 2022 Initial version.

1. Introduction

"The language of Giza is mathematics."

Robert Bauval

"You will believe."

The architects of Giza

In my paper, Khufu's Coffin (Douglas, 2021) [1], I proposed an "original location" for the coffin in

the Great Pyramid, close to where it is now, being φ^2 and ρ^3 cubits from the west and north walls, respectively.

However, due to other considerations which will presently be shown, I was never really happy with that location. The astronomical alignment suggested a different location, but I needed more. So I sat on the idea for over a year. I recently came across the very interesting paper by Dr. Chetansing Rajput, Golden Ratio [2], which provided the necessary “missing link” confirmation of my suspected location. I now present the new location, which is in about the same line East-West, but closer to the southern wall. A fringe benefit is further confirmation of the stellar alignment proposed in Zep Tepi Mathematics 101 (Douglas, 2021) (ZTM101) [3].

2. Notation, accuracy and methodology

2.1 Notation

I take the royal cubit as $\pi/6$ metres, to 4 decimal places. (*The Beautiful Cubit System*, Douglas 2019 [4]). While working on ZTM101 it became apparent they thought 3 or 4 decimals were accurate enough, so I have used that, and things “just work.” Three or four decimals is appropriate for a culture that may have done their calculations using a counting table, abacus, or slide rule.

Symbols used in this and other papers:

Symbol	Name	Approximate / practical value	% Accuracy to true
π	Archimedes' constant	3.1416	99.9998
φ	Golden ratio	1.618 $\varphi + 1 = \varphi^2 = 2.618$	99.9979
ρ	Plastic number / ratio	1.3247 $\rho + 1 = \rho^3 = 2.3247$	99.9986
♁	Royal cubit aka cubit	0.5236 m ($\pi/6$)	
"	Petrie inches	0.025399977 m	

Table 1: Symbols, names and values

I use “cubit” for Royal cubit ♁.

When Petrie took his measurements, his inch was 25.399977mm [5] rather than the current 25.4mm. To convert his inches to ♁, I use a conversion factor of 20.61419189, from

$$\frac{0.5236}{0.025399977} = 20.61419189$$

Petrie concluded, based on his measurements of the King's Chamber, that the ♁ was $20.620'' \pm 0.005''$, which is 0.5236205259 to 0.5238745256 m.

Petrie took his measurements after at least one major (in 1303) and several lesser earthquakes (*Sustainability problems of the Giza pyramids*, Hemeda and Sonbol [6], as well as the activities of the explosive Howard Vyse (*Operations carried on at the pyramids of Gizeh in 1837*, Vyse and Perring [7] As a result, the walls could have shifted slightly. Also, everyone assumes the chamber was built 100% perfectly, which may not be true.

3. Determining the location

We don’t know the original placement of the coffin within the king’s chamber.

It had clearly been moved when Petrie measured it, and the pebble underneath the coffin was probably there to help with moving, since its mass is over 3000 kg.

Petrie gives the distances from the corners (NE, NW and SW, top and base) to the north and west walls, in inches, as

	<i>NE to N wall</i>	<i>NW to N wall</i>	<i>NW to W wall</i>	<i>SW to S wall</i>
Top	47.70	48.90	53.34	56.50
Base	48.35	50.06	53.32	56.54

Table 2: Petrie's distances to the nearest walls

In Khufu’s Coffin, I proposed that it was originally 2.3247G, or ρ³G from the north wall, and 2.618G, or φ²G from the west wall. Diagrammatically, it looks as in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: My original proposed location for the coffin.

The red bar in Fig 1 is the entrance, the blue bars are the air shafts, and the green bars are the suspected entrances.

The path to the new location starts with the site map. In ZTM101, I proposed a site plan as in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Giza site plan.

This site plan is mathematically developed, and based on a stellar arrangement at around 55.5k BCE, as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: The stellar inspiration for the site plan.

The observant reader may have noticed that this site plan is a double square, just like the king's chamber. So what happens when we merge them?

Figure 4: The site plan merged with the king's chamber floor.

The first thing that jumps out is how well P1 matches the entrance. It is also curious that P6 is at a suspected entrance. The northern air shaft lines up reasonably well with the edge of P2. The coffin centre lines up reasonably well with the southern edge of P5. Some other curiosities will be discussed in a separate paper.

Things get more interesting when we add the stars back.

Figure 5: Merging the stars, site plan and king's chamber.

Consider the position of the coffin, and the head of Draco... the group of four stars including Eltanin and Rastaban, also known as the lozenge. It is almost as if this is representing a head, and that the coffin should encompass it. Indeed, the width of the lozenge is almost the same as the width of the coffin.

I puzzled over this diagram for more than a year, looking for stories related to Draco that might provide a clue. The problem is that my proposed construction date of 55.5k BCE means it is unlikely that any mythologies of that era were passed down to the present or near-past.

While we map those stars to the asterism Draco, other cultures see different patterns. Here are a selection of screenshots from the Kstars astronomy program.

Figure 6: Current conventional Western asterisms.

Figure 7: Alternate Western asterisms.

Figure 8: Other known names for some asterisms.

Note that Draco's head is also called the lozenge.

Figure 9: Norse asterisms.

Figure 10: Lakota Sioux asterisms.

Figure 11: Korean asterisms.

Figure 12: Egyptian Asterisms

Figure 13: Chinese asterisms.

Different cultures see different things, so we can not assume that Draco is at all relevant.

I puzzled over moving the coffin to encompass the lozenge. Even if I did, should the lozenge match where a head might go (assuming the coffin was actually intended for a body), or should it align with the centre? I needed another clue, and it duly came along.

In his paper on the golden ratio [2], Dr. Rajput points out that the incircle in a golden ratio triangle, defined as a $1 : 2 : \sqrt{5}$ triangle, divides the height in the golden ratio.

Figure 14: Golden triangle with incircle and ϕ divisor.

If we put two of these triangles together with a common hypotenuse, then we get a double square, as in the site plan and king's chamber. On the site plan, this produces Fig.15.

Figure 15: Stars, site plan, golden triangles and incircles.

The centre of the blue incircle is close to the centre of P2, and to the star Alioth.

Similarly, the centre of the green incircle is close to the star Eltanin... in a mirror relationship to the blue circle. I took this as the clue I needed to relocate the coffin, which gives us the new location, centered in the incircle.

Figure 16: Stars, site plan and king's chamber with new coffer location.

Some observations:

1. The centre of P2 aligns very closely with the top of the coffer. The actual y-coordinates (in metres) are 554.215 for P2 centre, versus 553.914 for the top edge of the coffer... a difference of 30cm on the site plan, and nothing when scaled to the chamber dimensions.
2. The bottom edge of the coffer aligns reasonably with the possible entrance on the west wall.
3. Larry Pahl [8] suggested that possibly the coffer should be sited so that the centre-line of the pyramid ran through the middle. Petrie [9] says that the west wall is 107.7 ± 3.0 " west of the pyramid centre line. If we take the maximum value of 110.7 ", then that line aligns well with the right edge of the coffer. The centre line x-co-ordinate is 628, versus 630.279 for the right edge of the coffer, a difference of 2.279 m on the site plan and 1 cm when scaled to the chamber size. The line also aligns with the possible edge of the entrance on the north wall, which has x-co-ordinate 633.242, about 1.5 cm further east when scaled to chamber size.
4. The horizontal line through the centre of the coffer divides the chamber in the golden ratio.
5. The right edge neatly bisects the lozenge. This suggests, if the coffer was actually for a body, that the lozenge was seen as a "door" or "portal" between the world of the living and the world of the dead. It may have been ritualistic rather than practical.
6. Draco snakes through the possible entrance on the north wall.
7. We can follow a similar approach to ZTM101, where the pyramids divide the spaces in

irrational ratios. The coffin nearly divides the vertical space between P1 south and P6 north, as well as the horizontal space between P6 east and P4 west, in the $\sqrt{\phi^3}$ ratio. The ratios are 2.0724 in the x direction, and 2.0623 in the y direction. $\sqrt{\phi^3}$ is 2.05817. The centre co-ordinates are (520.8467; 808.383), the ideal spot giving exact values for $\sqrt{\phi^3}$ would be (517.14711; 810.5152), a difference of about 4.3 m on the site plan, or about 2 cm when scaled to the chamber.

Figure 17: How the coffin divides the spaces.

This of course begs the question whether there was such a huge construction on the site. “Tony Bushby,” writing in “The Secret in the Bible,” [10] drops a hint about a large building west of the Khufu pyramid. I don’t know if that refers to this.

Another possibility is that the coffin was orientated lengthwise with the chamber, as in Fig. 18. I don’t see anything interesting with the alignments or spacing in this configuration.

Figure 18: King's chamber with rotated coffer.

4. Conclusion

On one level, trying to figure out where the coffer was originally may seem like a pointless exercise.

On the other hand, if the proposed location, which makes geometric and astronomical sense, is correct, it provides further support to my proposed stellar alignment, and hence also the date circa 55.5k BCE.

Perhaps other interesting ideas may surface from this plan of the king's chamber.

5. Acknowledgements

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6. Bibliography

- [1] I. Douglas, 'Khufu's Coffin', Zenodo, Sep. 2021. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5539862.
- [2] D. C. Rajput, 'Golden Ratio', *JOURNAL OF ADVANCES IN MATHEMATICS*, vol. 20, pp. 19–42, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.24297/jam.v20i.8945.
- [3] I. Douglas, 'Zep Tepi Mathematics 101', Zenodo, Jan. 2021. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4410650.

- [4] Douglas, Ian, 'The Beautiful Cubit System'. Jun. 30, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3263864>
- [5] 'Inch', *Wikipedia*. Sep. 15, 2021. Accessed: Sep. 18, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Inch&oldid=1044507780>
- [6] S. Hemeda and A. Sonbol, 'Sustainability problems of the Giza pyramids', *Heritage Science*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 8, Jan. 2020, doi: 10/gmt927.
- [7] R. W. H. Howard-Vyse and J. S. Perring, *Operations carried on at the pyramids of Gizeh in 1837: with an account of a voyage into Upper Egypt, and an appendix*. London, J. Fraser, 1840. Accessed: Sep. 18, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://archive.org/details/operationscarrie01howa>
- [8] 'Larry Pahl - Academia.edu'. <https://independent.academia.edu/LarryPahl> (accessed May 12, 2022).
- [9] W. M. F. (William M. F. Petrie, *The pyramids and temples of Gizeh*. London: Field & Tuer; New York: Scribner & Welford, 1883. Accessed: Sep. 18, 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://archive.org/details/cu31924012038927>
- [10] T. Bushby, *The Secret in the Bible*, 1st edition. Maroochydore, Qld.: Stanford Publishing Group, 2003.
- [11] C. Maclennan, *Libertinus font*. 2020. Accessed: Jan. 01, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/alquerque/libertinus>